

ISLAMIC EDUCATION THOUGHTS

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Abstract

This paper will review the Biography of Hasan Langgulung, his works, the concept of Islamic education thought according to Hasan Langgulung and the relevance of Hasan Langgulung Islamic Education Thought to Current Education. Therefore, this idea can be a reference for improving education in Indonesia, especially Islamic education and become a reference for teachers in doing better learning.

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A. Introduction

In essence, education is an effort to pass on values, which will be a helper and guide for mankind in living life and at the same time to improve the fate and civilization of mankind. Without education, it is certain that today's humans are no different from past generations of humans. Therefore, in an extreme way, it can be said that going back and forth or the good or bad civilization of a society or nation is largely determined by how the educational process is carried out by the people of that nation. As Islamic education aims to develop human potential and be able to behave well in accordance with Islamic principles, making the Qur'an and Hadith as a guide in guiding life and achieving the perfection of life, all of this can be obtained through education. Good education will lead humans to become human beings and can carry out God's mandate properly to become caliph fil al-ardhi. This heavy task requires humans to have a good education. Efforts to improve education continue to be made, starting from the curriculum, educational objectives, methods that must be used during teaching and learning, strategies that must be used and others related to education.

One of the educational figures who contributed a lot of his thoughts in the world of education, especially Islamic education, was Hasan Langgulung.

This paper will review the Biography of Hasan Langgulung, his works, the concept of Islamic education thought according to Hasan Langgulung and the relevance of Hasan Langgulung Islamic Education Thought to Current Education. Therefore, this idea can be a reference for improving education in Indonesia, especially Islamic education and become a reference for teachers in doing better learning.

ISLAMIC EDUCATION THOUGHTS

Etymologically, thinking comes from the root word "think" (from Arabic *فكر*, which means the process, method, or activity of thinking, which is using the mind to decide a problem by considering everything wisely. In other words, thinking is an intelligent effort from the working process of the mind and heart to see symptoms and try to find solutions wisely (A. Susanto, 2009: 2-3).

While education is a process of preparing the younger generation to run life and fulfill their life goals more effectively and efficiently (Azra, 2002: 3). Education is not only a transfer of knowledge, but also a transformation of values and character building with all its aspects. While teaching is the process of transferring knowledge from a teacher (teacher) to the person being taught (students, students, students).

Education is the process of forming individuals based on Islamic teachings to achieve high degrees so that they are able to carry out their duties to their caliphate and succeed in realizing happiness in the world and the hereafter (Nata, 2010: 10). So Islamic education is wider in scope and has a higher purpose because it not only produces people who are knowledgeable and capable of carrying out leadership tasks in the world, but also creates people who are happy servants of God (the hereafter).

Islamic education is different from secular (Western) education which only forms human beings who are smart in their fields (specialists) and focuses on achieving mere physical or material happiness and does not care about the moral aspect, so that the products are intellectual but immoral and morally human beings. It is easy for them to use their knowledge for the sake of individual interests, not for the benefit of the people. Islamic education is more directing humans to achieve happiness in the world and the hereafter in a balanced way, knowing how to have good morals towards Allah as the Creator, towards fellow humans and other creatures of God.

In terminology, Islamic education thinking is a series of mind and heart work processes that are carried out seriously in looking at the various problems that exist in Islamic education and trying to build an educational paradigm that is able to become a vehicle for the complete coaching and development of students (A. Susanto, 2009). : 3-4). So, through this approach, it is hoped that Islamic education will be able to lead students to become fully human, not only intelligent and knowledgeable, but also have good morals.

2. Thoughts on Islamic Education in the Golden Age of Islam

Islamic history records that the Abbasid period was the "golden age" of Islam, especially during the reign of Harun al-Rashid and al-Makmum, because of the intellectual sciences such as philosophy, geometry, mathematics, astronomy, chemistry, history, and geography. At this time it has begun to enter and emerge, the development of educational institutions, as well as the birth of great educational ideas. It is not surprising that at this time there were prominent ulama (imam) such as Imam Abu Hanifah (80-150 H), Imam Malik (95-179 H), Imam Shafi'i (150-204), Imam Ahmad bin Hambal (164-241 H). H), known as *Aimmatu mazahib al-Arba'ah* (four imams of fiqh schools) which is still followed by Muslims around the world. In addition, the famous *Imam al-Muhadditsin also appeared* , namely Imam al-Bukhari (A. Susanto, 2009: 29).

During the reign of Harun al-Rashid and continued by al-Makmum, there was a massive translation movement of Greek, Persian, and Indian science and philosophy into Arabic. As a result, some of the Muslim scholars were influenced by foreign knowledge, especially Greek science and philosophy. The works of Greek philosophers such as Plato and Aristotle are considered as very important as the Qur'an. In this regard, Muslim intellectuals began to interpret Islamic teachings within the framework of Aristotle's thought and sought to harmonize Islamic teachings with Greek philosophy. Of course, this in turn gave rise to many philosophical doctrines that contradict each other as the Mu'tazilah demonstrated (Alavi, 2003: 4). The Abbasid rulers who supported the Mu'tazilah madhhab, especially al-Makmum enforced this notion by force and did not hesitate to kill and imprison the ulama' who did not want to follow their madhhab.

During the Abbasid period, training was held for previously unknown madrasas. The person who first founded the madrasa was Prime Minister Nizham al-Mulk. The coaching of these madrasas shows the peak of Islamic school education (A. Susanto, 2009: 30).

The most important feature of this golden age of Islam is the emergence of Islamic educational thoughts. Muslim scholars at this time competed to write books on education and teaching in a broad and deep manner which indicated a special attention in the field of education. Ibn Sahnun (3rd century H), was the first to write a book on education, followed by al-Qabisi (4th century H), Ibn Maskawaih and al-Ghazali (6th century H), Ibn Khaldun (4th century H), -8 H). During this period, the author of a book on education named Burhanuddin al-Zarnuji appeared with his monumental work *Ta'lim al-Muta'allim* (A. Susanto, 2009: 30), which until now is still taught in Islamic boarding schools or schools. *salaf* and become the main reference in teaching ethics and correct learning procedures in the Islamic world.

3. Educational Practices in the Islamic Golden Age

Education in this golden age in practice is divided into two levels, namely the level of basic education and the level of further education. In basic education, students learn to read, write, Arabic grammar, philology, ethics and the practice of worship (*salat*). Learning to read the Qur'an and practice worship is mandatory. Break time is done at the discretion of the students. At the advanced level of education, in addition to learning the language of the Qur'an and al-Hadith, there are also Arabic lessons, literature, philosophy and others (Alavi, 2003: 4-5).

Education in this period was carried out in the following institutions:

a. *Kuttab* (basic education)

Kuttab or *maktab* was known before the arrival of Islam, which is a place to learn to write. After the arrival of Islam, *kuttab* increasingly developed because Islam strongly encouraged its people to read (S. Al -' Alaq: 1-5). At the beginning of Islam, the subject matter in the *kuttab* was only reading and writing about poetry, and it was carried out in the homes of the teachers concerned. Then at the end of the first century Hijriyah, lessons in *kuttab* developed, in addition to reading and writing lessons, they were also taught how to read the Qur'an and the main points of religious teachings (Zuhairi, 2004: 91).

In the golden age of Islam (starting in the 8th century AD), *kuttab* began to teach general sciences other than religious knowledge. This is due to the influence of *Hellenistic culture* that brought changes in the field of Islamic education curriculum . In subsequent developments, *kuttab* is divided into two, namely *kuttab* which teaches religious sciences and *kuttab* which teaches general sciences. Study time at the *pole* from Saturday morning to Thursday with details: *morning-dhuha* with the material of the Koran, *dhuha-zuhur* with

writing material, *ba'da zuhur-afternoon* with Arabic grammar, history, mathematics (Nata, 2010: 33-34).

b. Low education in the Palace

The education of palace children is almost the same as in *kuttab*, the difference is that in the palace the students' parents (caliphate or palace officials) are those who make lesson plans that are aligned with their children and the goals desired by their parents. The teacher in the palace was called a *muaddib*, because his job was to teach character and pass on the intellectuals and knowledge of the previous people to the children of officials. The emergence of education in the palace was based on the idea that education must be prepared to prepare students to be capable of carrying out their duties later as adults (Zuhairi, 2004: 92).

c. *Halaqah* (study group)

The teaching and learning process at the *halaqah* is carried out where students sit around the teacher, while the teacher explains, reads his essay, or comments on the work of others. *Halaqah* activities can be done in the mosque or in the houses of scholars'. Education in *halaqah* is included in the category of advanced education (Nata, 2010:34-35).

d. Bookshops

At first the book shops only functioned as a place to sell books by scholars or poets. Since the book sellers are mostly intelligent poets who have chosen to work as book sellers in order to get many opportunities to read, study, and socialize with scholars and poets, eventually the book shops developed into gathering places for scholars and intellectuals to discuss, debate, and exchange ideas on various scientific issues. Thus, the book store functions as an educational institution in the context of developing science and culture (Zuhiri, 2004: 94).

e. The houses of the scholars' (*manazil al-ulama'*)

Many of the *ulama'* houses were used as teaching places because the *ulama'* could not give lessons in mosques or madrasas, while many students were interested in learning knowledge from these *ulama'*. The scholars' whose homes became places for teaching and learning, for example: the house of al-Ghazali, Ibn Sina, Ali Ibn Muhammad al-Fasihi, Ya'qub Ibn Killis, Wazir Khalifah al - 'Aziz billah al-Fathimy, and others (Zuhairi, 2004: 95)

f. *Majlis or literary saloon*

literary saloon was a special place held by the caliph to discuss various disciplines. This *literary saloon* increasingly experienced extraordinary progress during the Caliph Harun al-Rashid because the caliph himself had intelligence and loved science so much that he himself was actively involved in it. The caliph often invited jurists to debate, poets to compete, linguists, and scientists to discuss various sciences, as well as art experts and poets to take part in competitions (Zuhairi, 2004: 95-96).

g. Hospital

During the heyday of Islam, the caliph established many hospitals. The function of the hospital at that time was not only to treat and treat sick people, but also to educate personnel related to care and treatment. They conducted experiments in the fields of medicine and pharmacy. The hospital is also a place for practicum for medical schools outside the hospital. Thus the hospital also functions as an educational institution. In Baghdad until 116 AD there were 60 medical institutions, Cairo 5 hospitals, and Cardova and Seville had medical centers (Nata, 2010: 41).

h. Library

Libraries in the Islamic world during the golden age had become an important cultural aspect, as well as a place of learning and a source of scientific development. For example, *Bait al-Hikmah*, the library built by Caliph Harun a-Rashid, is a place for study and discussion like a university. The most complete and largest library in the Islamic world contains Islamic religious sciences and Arabic, various kinds of knowledge that have developed at that time, as well as various kinds of translated books from Greek, Persian, Indian, and others (Zuhairi, 2004:98).

i. *Badiyah* (desert, village where *Bedouins* live)

After the relationship with the Arabs with non-Arabs, the Arabs became corrupted, the Arabs became not fluent in the language, did not know the rules of the Arabic language. Therefore, whoever wants to learn pure and fluent Arabic, he must go to the Bedouin village. No wonder many of the children of the caliph, the ulama', and scientists went to the institutes to study Arabic language and literature. Thus, the institutions have functioned as educational institutions (Nata, 2010:42).

j. Mosque

In the golden age of Islam, the mosques established by the rulers were generally equipped with various means and facilities for education. A place for children's education, places for recitation of the ulema'-ulama' who form *halaqah-halaqah*, a place for discussion and debate in various sciences, and also equipped with a library room with books from various kinds of science that are sufficient many. Imam Shafi'I is in charge of teaching the interpretation of the Qur'an, al-Hadith, Philosophy, Rhetoric, Arabic Grammar, and Poetry. Meanwhile, at-Tabary taught poetry at the Amar mosque, while al-Jubai al-Mu'tazily became a philosophy lecturer at the Basrah mosque.

k. Madrasah

Thus the mosque in the Islamic world, throughout its history, has played a central role, besides its function as a place to communicate with God, as an educational institution and a communication center for fellow Muslims.

The emergence of formal educational institutions in the form of madrasas during the heyday of Islam was a development of the education and teaching system that was previously carried out in mosques. The main reason for the establishment of madrasas outside the mosque is that the existence and activities of *halaqah-halaqah* (study groups) inside the mosque often interfere with people wanting to worship in the mosque, while the function of the mosque is for worship activities. Besides, the development of science gave birth to *halaqah-halaqah* whose numbers could not possibly be accommodated in the mosque (Zuhairi, 2004: 100-101).

The Abbasid rulers had great interest in madrasas as official educational institutions. At that time, the popular madrasa was the Nizhamiyah madrasa which was founded by the prime minister Nizham al-Mulk in 1067 AD/459 H. The madrasa was an official educational institution and the government was actively involved in setting its goals, outlining the curriculum, appointing teachers, and channel funds regularly to him (Maksum, 1999: 61).

The education system of the Nizhamiyah Madrasah Baghdad (Nata, 2010: 65-71) is:

1) The main objectives of Nizamiyah madrasa education are: *first* , to prepare prospective Sunni scholars to face the Shi'ite thought movement, *second* , to provide competent Sunni teachers to teach and spread Sunni schools to other areas. *Third*, forming a group of Sunni employees to participate in running the government, heading their offices, especially in the fields of justice and management.

2) The curriculum and teaching methods of Madrasah Nazhimiyyah are focused on the Qur'an (reading, memorizing, and writing), Arabic literature, the history of the Prophet Muhammad. And Mathematics, with an emphasis on the Shafi'i school and the Asy'ariyah theological system. In other words, Madrasah Nazhimiyyah concentrates its efforts on *ulum al-shari'ah* and *ushul al-din* according to the goals that have been set for it. Consequently, Madrasah Nazhimiyyah ignores practical applied sciences (*al-ulum al-tathbiqiyah al-amaliyah*). In Madrasah Nazhimiyyah the teacher delivers the subject matter (lectures/talqin) by standing in front of the class, while the students sit and listen at the small tables provided. Then proceed with dialogue or discussion (*munaqasah*) between teachers and students about the material presented in an atmosphere of high scientific spirit. The science of fiqh is described by the teacher in a syllabus called *ta'liqah* . The work is compiled by each teacher based on his lecture notes when he was a student, his readings, and his personal conclusions on related topics . Some students copy the *ta'liqah* by means of a dictation process, while others provide notes from class discussions or from their own research, so that their *ta'liqah* is more of their personal reflection on the lecture material delivered by the lecturers.

3) The teaching staff and students of Madrasah Nazhimiyyah Baghdad are selected staff and students through a rigorous selection process. This is because Madrasah Nazhimiyyah is a higher education institution that teaches higher education as well. Only eminent ulama' at that time and well-known and competent professors in their fields were chosen to teach. The teachers were appointed by the caliph and served for a certain period. In carrying out his duties a teacher is assisted by an assistant whose job is to explain parts that are difficult to understand after giving a lecture, or help

students who are less intelligent. Nizham al-Mulk also gave scholarships and provided dormitories for free, and was even given enough shopping money.

4) Funding and Facilities for Madrasah Nazhimiyyah Baghdad are provided by waqf institutions. Prime Minister Nizham al-Mulk provided waqf funds to finance teachers, Imams, students who received scholarships and boarding facilities, and established Nizhamiyah Madrasas in almost all of the Seljuq territory at that time, established a library with approximately 6,000 volumes of books complete with catalogs. , then set the budget for the entire madrasa at 600,000 dinars per year, while for the Nizhamiyah Madrasah Baghdad only one tenth, that is, 60,000 dinars per year. This is sufficient to finance the various facilities provided for students and teachers, in the form of accommodation, meals and allowances.

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